

DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS BETWEEN CAMEROON AND TURKEY: A BENEFICIAL COOPERATION THAT HAS COME TO STAY

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ABSTRACT

Interests of sovereign states transcend across friendships of individuals, commonalities in cultures and beliefs and most importantly, economic gains (the genesis of constant competition for expansion and hegemony in today's international system). More so, there seems to be a need to analyze the interest of Turkey in one of Africa's most emergent countries, and Turkey's close ally in Central Africa, Cameroon. It has been a period of cordial diplomatic relationship between the two countries and continue to be so beneficial for the two countries in the political, economic and socio-cultural domains. Diplomatic cooperation between Cameroon and Turkey that officially began in the 1960s had so far come with immense ramifications most especially on the side of the Cameroon government who have benefitted and continue to benefit from the aids of the Turkish government. The cooperation had transcend just political relations, but has extend to economic, social and cultural milieus. Therefore, this paper analyzes the diplomatic win-win cooperation between Turkey and Cameroon. The study uses the chronological and thematic research methods by critically analyzing existing relevant studies published in books and articles. Findings show that the relationship between the two countries dates back to the Pre- colonial period. However, official diplomatic cooperation were established between both countries in the 1960s. From all indications, it is a friendly and beneficial relationship that has come to stay.

Keywords: Cameroon, Turkey, Diplomatic Cooperation, Ramifications, Relationship.

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INTRODUCTION

One of those Muslim countries that Cameroon long established diplomatic relations or ties with is Turkey. It should be emphasis here that cooperation between Cameroon and Turkey (the then Ottoman Empire) goes back to the pre-colonial period. However, official Diplomatic relations between Cameroon and Turkey began in the early 1960s and was strengthened in the 1970s and 1980s. At the beginning of this diplomatic ties, Cameroon was under the regime of President Ahmadou Ahidjo, who was later succeeded by President Paul Biya. Turkey on the other hand from 1960 was under the leadership of President Cevdet Sunay, who was later replaced or succeeded by President Tekin Arıburun, then replaced by Fahri Kouturk and finally Ihran Sabri. (Elliot Florence, 1973: 12-78)

Turkey and Cameroon are located on two different continents of the world. Despite the commonality of religion (Islam) that Turkey shares with population of Cameroon, it is hard to project the outcome of such beneficial relationship that has existed for centuries, long before the Republics of Cameroon and Turkey were born. Although located on different continents, the peoples of Cameroon and Turkey seem to have much in common. Each of them consists of a great mosaic of different ethnic origins that assemble under one flag in the form of nation-state. Throughout history, the territory of modern Turkey has been the cradle of several civilizations embracing various cultures. Thanks to this geographical location and her historical background, Turkey is today endowed with the cultural richness of her people. A similar richness manifests itself in Cameroon society even more remarkably as the people of Cameroon is composed of over 250 ethnic groups. (Elliot Florence, 1973: 12-78)

Naturally, this is not the only thing both countries have in common. Trade between these two peoples goes back centuries, long before the foundations of the present states of the Republic of Turkey and of the Republic of Cameroon. As early as the sixteenth century Turkish goods were traded on the streets of Adamawa, one of the northern regions of modern Cameroon.

These centuries-old relationships and contacts between the peoples of Turkey and Cameroon have been upheld and maintained by modern Turkey and Cameroon from the latter's independence from the French and British colonial rule in 1960 and 1961. (Ngho, 1996: 40-197). Turkey later established a consulate general in Cameroon political capital Yaounde during the era of the Biya regime. Victor Tchatchouw was the first residents Cameroon Ambassador to Ankara, Turkey. He was appointed in December 2018 by President Paul Biya. However, it should be noted that relations between Cameroon and Turkey were initially good and friendly especially under President Ahmadou Ahidjo. This was mostly due to the fact that President Ahidjo was also a Muslim just like the three Turkish Presidents enumerated above. However, relations between Cameroon and Turkey considerably improved also under President Paul Biya. This may be due to the diplomatic or foreign policy of President Paul Biya in relation to the Muslim world or countries. Moreover, Paul Biya attempted to develop a freer and more democratic Cameroon with more freedom of speech, liberty and freedom of worship. (Ngho, 1996: 40-197). Before deeply analyzing the diplomatic relations between Cameroon and Turkey, let us first of all present Cameroon and Turkey geographically and historically.

Geographical location of Cameroon

Cameroon is situated in Central Africa, at the juncture of the Gulf of Guinea. It is bounded on the North by Chad, on the East by the Central African Republic, on the South by Congo, Gabon and Equatorial Guinea and on the West by Nigeria. Cameroon is a country with Ten Regions and several major towns, amongst which are Yaounde, the political capital of the country, with about one million or more inhabitants. Douala, which is the major economic city has more than two million inhabitants.

The other major towns are Garoua, Bafoussam, Maroua, Bamenda, Ngaoundere, Ebolowa, Buea and Bertoua. Cameroon has more than 240 tribes and two official languages which are English and French: Cameroon is a secular state. Two major religions have followers; Christianity and Islam. Animism is also widely practiced. The country has two major seasons which are the dry and rainy seasons.

Historically, Cameroon was administered by the Germans from 1884 to 1916. According to V.J. Ngoh, when the Germans were ousted from the country by the joint British and French forces during the First World War, there was a joint administration of the territory by the British and French referred to as the Condominium. From 1922 to 1939, Cameroon was a Mandated Territory of the League of Nations still administered by Britain and France. From 1945 to 1960/61, British and French Cameroons were Trust territories of the United Nations. French Cameroon got her Independence on 1st January, 1960, while British Cameroons got her own Independence on October 1st, 1961. On that very date of October 1st, 1961, Reunification of British and French Cameroons took place under the United Nations supervision.

Geographical and Historical Presentation of Turkey

Turkey according to Florence Elliott is an Independent state in Asia Minor, and partly in Eastern Europe. The country cover an area of 294, 502 sq.m. The current population of based on worldometer elaboration of the latest United Nations data. The former population estimate beginning 2020 was 84,339, 067 people. It should be noted that 99% of the Turkish populations are Muslims. The capital of Turkey is Ankara. (Elliot Florence, 1973: 12-78)

The Ottoman Empire, which once extended from Morocco along the North African coast to Cairo, included eastern Europe as far as the Adriatic sea, and had its eastern boundaries on the Caspian sea, collapsed after the First World War. A Turkish Republic was set-up in 1923 under the Presidency of Kemal Atatürk (1881-1938) Atatürk Assumed dictatorial powers, separated church and state, banned polygamy, the veil and the Fez, ordered Turks to wear European clothes, abolished titles, abandoned Arabic in favour of Latin script, suppressed communism, took the first census, developed industries, and generally westernized Turkey. (Hitti P., 1970: pp. 90-170).

The Republican Peoples Party, founded by Atatürk, with a policy of nationalism, Laicism, and *étatisme* (state control of the economy) was virtually the only political party for many years.

However, after some encouragement from the government, the Democratic Party was created. According to Elliot Florence (1973: 12-78), it first came to power in 1950. In the elections of October 1957, under Adam Menderes, it won 48% of the votes cast as opposed to the 41% for the Republican People's Party. After the Coup d'état of 27 May 1960 by General Cemal Gürsel, he abrogated the constitution of 1924 and ruled by a committee of National Union.

Turkey, an independent state partly in Asia Minor, and partly in Eastern Europe; area 294,502 sq. m.; population (1971) 36,910,000, of whom 99 per cent are Moslems; capital Ankara. The Ottoman Empire, which once extended from Morocco along the North African coast to Cairo, included eastern Europe as far as the Adriatic Sea, and had its eastern boundaries on the Caspian Sea, collapsed after the First World War. A Turkish Republic was set up in 1923 under the Presidency of Kemal Atatürk (1881-1938). Atatürk assumed dictatorial powers, separated Church and State, banned polygamy, the veil and the fez, ordered Turks to wear European clothes, abolished titles, abandoned Arabic in favour of a Latin script, suppressed Communism, took the first census, developed industries, and generally westernized Turkey.

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At elections held in October 1961, under the new Constitution of that year, the Republican People's Party, led by Ismet İnönü, won 173 seats in the Grand National Assembly; the Justice Party which, to some extent, carried on the tradition of the outlawed Democratic Party won 158 seats. On 26 October Gürsel was elected President for a seven-year term by the necessary two-thirds majority of both the Senate and the Grand National Assembly. In November 1961 İnönü formed a coalition with the Justice Party until December 1963 when he joined with the independents in a minority government. He resigned in February 1965 after his government had been defeated in the Assembly; this was said to be the first time in Turkish parliamentary history that a government had been brought down by an adverse vote. He was succeeded by Zuyat Hayri İnönü Ürgüplü, an independent allied to the Justice Party who committed his government to immediate social reform. (Beshir, 1982: 78-88) However, the elections held in October 1965 gave a decisive majority to the Justice Party (240 out of the 450 seats) and its leader, Suleyman Demirel, became Prime Minister.

In 1970 a split occurred in the Justice Party, the expelled members founding a new Democratic Party to press for speedier reforms; the government was defeated in the Assembly and extremist violence broke out, involving the kidnapping of U.S. servicemen. The Air Force Commander demanded social reform, and especially agrarian reform, higher pay for the armed services and a more equitable tax system, as a 'matter of urgency', and under military pressure for a 'strong and credible government' Demirel resigned in March 1971. President Sunay (elected 1968 to succeed Gürsel) appointed an R.P.P. lawyer, Dr Nihat Erim, to lead a coalition government which would implement the reforms promised in the 1961 Constitution. At elections held in November 1971 the Justice Party suffered an electoral reverse, winning only 222 (257 in October 1969) seats; the splinter Democratic Party won 41 seats, and the R.P.P., whose right-wing had seceded rather than participate in the Erim government, won 140 seats (144 in 1969). Following further outbreaks of anarchic violence, the murder of three foreign radar technicians by members of the Turkish Liberation Movement, and the unwillingness of the major parties to grant exceptional powers to the government to deal with the crisis, Erim resigned in April 1972. Ferit Melen, of the National Reliance Party, then formed a government pledged to restore order and reform. (Elliot Florence, 1973: 12-78)

Eighty per cent of the population work on the land, where there has been extensive mechanization of agriculture; there are considerable exports of grain, tobacco, cotton, and dried fruit. The output of Turkish metals (iron, chrome, copper, and manganese), which find a ready market for hard currency, has also been greatly expanded. Nearly 700,000 Turks are employed as 'guest workers' in Germany, the Netherlands and Switzerland.

According to Elliot Florence, the increase in productivity, the liberal distribution by the government of agricultural credits and subsidies, and the devotion to defence of sums equal to half of the budget, have combined with the rise in world prices to produce inflation and budget deficits. The extraction of taxes, especially from the landowners and farmers, is made difficult by the fact that all the political parties are closely associated with strong feudal interests.

In the Second World War, Turkey, whose active support of the allied powers would probably have involved occupation by Germany and liberation by the U.S.S.R., chose to remain neutral. Its present commitments are to Yugoslavia and Greece (under the Balkan Pact, q.v.), to Pakistan, Persia, and the U.K. (Central Treaty Organization, q.v.), and, as a member of N.A.T.O., to the North Atlantic Treaty powers. There is a long-standing fear of the U.S.S.R.; in 1945 the Russians denounced their Treaty of Neutrality, Non-Aggression, and International Co-operation which had been signed in 1925. The Dardanelles, which are part of the straits connecting the Mediterranean with the Black Sea, are of strategic significance. (Elliot Florence, 1973: 12-78)

Cameroon Turkey: Focus on Intensifying Ties

Cameroon and Turkey in the late 1990s and early 2000s have been concerting with each other on better ways to strengthen their diplomatic relations. These talks had mostly taking place in between the Cameroonian authorities and Turkey authorities. Most often than not, the Turkish ambassador to Cameroon was is that countries diplomatic representative had always represented his country. This was the Case in 2013 with the Turkey Ambassador to Cameroon, Omer Faruk Dogan who was received by the Cameroonian head of state, President Paul Biya.

Ambassador Omer Faruk Dogan in an audience with the head of state of Cameroon Paul Biya on Friday the 12th of April 2013, expressed his gratitude and thankfulness to the Cameroonian head of state for receiving him as the new Turkish Ambassador to Cameroon. The said that Turkey was totally committed to support and accompany Cameroon in its effort to become an emerging economy. The ambassador told the press about some of the projects he discussed with the head of state, including the opening of two major learning institutions in Douala and Yaounde, the construction of a district hospital in Yaounde, and the construction of roads, dams and other development projects all over the country. Ambassador Omer Faruk Dogan was of the opinion that the implementation of the BOT (Build, Operate, Transfer) system will be most Suitable for projects that require massive financial inputs. (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2019: 3-17)

Following Eulalia Amabo's report, His Excellency Omer Faruk Dogan was happy that the recent visit of Paul Biya to Turkey was already yielding fruit or dividends, as a Turkish and Cameroonian Company have already signed an agreement worth over 50 Billion Francs CFA. He said that many more such projects were in the pipeline.

Ambassador Husnu Murat, who replaced Ambassador Omer Faruk Dogan in his farewell audience at the Ministry of External Relations in December 2018 Summed up bilateral relation between Cameroon and Turkey. He was of the opinion that Cameroon-Turkey Diplomatic Relations was in the right direction and that the partnership is strong. He went further to say that the relationship were solid and based on a true sense of brotherhood and solidarity. He said political dialogue had deepened between the two countries and concrete acts of solidarity manifested. He cited Turkey's support. (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2019: 3-17)

Political Dialogue between Cameroon and Turkey

In specific terms, Ambassador Husnu Murat ULKU was clear on the fact that political dialogue during his stay in Cameroon was deepened. The sense of solidarity was tested on many occasions. The two countries know that they can trust each other in any circumstance.

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He cited the high sense of solidarity demonstrated when Turkey had the shock of the coup attempt in 2016, and later when Cameroon faced so many security challenges. On the economic side, the ambassador said he was happy that the two countries have a vibrant partnership. The famous Japoma stadium in Douala once more will be the icon of that fruitful partnership. (Eulalia Amabo, 2020: 3-15)

The two days official visit to Cameroon of the Turkish President, Abdullah Gül

In order to reinforce and improve diplomatic ties between Cameroon and Turkey, the Turkish President Abdullah Gül visited Cameroon on the 16th of March 2010. The visit was also an occasion for the Turkish President to boost and diversify cooperation ties between the two countries. The two day official visit ended on March 17, and was marked by the beginning of a new era of bilateral cooperation between Cameroon and Turkey. (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2019: 3-17)

The very warm reception given the Turkish leader by President Paul Biya and the important agreements signed by the two countries will enable Cameroon to benefit from the rich experience of this emergent former "sick Man of Europe" with a population of 80 million inhabitants to resolve the tense security situation in Cameroon and rejoiced that Cameroon stood by Turkey during the foiled coup attempt in 2016. (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2019: 3-17)

Economic and social cooperation between Cameroon and Turkey

In the economic and Trade domains, the two countries are also strengthening ties. His Excellency, Husnu Murat was of the opinion that diplomatic relations is growing steadily between the two countries with reports stating that Cameroon exports to Turkey include timber, textiles, Petroleum and aluminum. Turkey is also interested in Cameroons's gas. In the sport infrastructure domain, a Turkish company is constructing the Japoma stadium in Cameroon's economic Capital, Douala. (Eulalia Amabo, 2020: 3-15)

In the same line, the Turkish Airlines fly to Cameroon's cities of Yaounde and Douala. In the educational sector, since 1992, many Cameroonian students are said to have benefitted from the Türkiye scholarship and others are through self-sponsor. Also, through the Turkish Cooperation and coordination Agency (TIKA), Turkey is providing development assistance to Cameroon in various domains. Turkish Foundation also has schools in Cameroon. (Eulalia Amabo, 2020: 3-15)

According to Ambassador Husnu Murat Ulku, political dialogue and solidarity between Cameroon and Turkey deepened during his three years diplomatic stay in Cameroon. The relations are solid based on a true sense of brotherhood and solidarity. There are concrete outcomes of the cooperation on the economic, social and security fronts. (Josy, 2017: 217-15)

According to Martin Nkemngu of Cameroon post line, the size and composition of the Turkish delegation of 150 persons, was a pointer to the determination of Ankara to give a new impetus to Turkey's relations, not only with Yaounde but also with others on the continent. President Abdullah Gül made it clear in a statement that Turkey would keep becoming the voice of Africa on international platform indicating that his country would increase its 18 embassies in Africa by 10.

Turkish businessmen according to the President can invest in the areas of mining, health and education in Cameroon. Turkey and Cameroon must work in an egalitarian manner. Win-win relationship. It was also a practical translation of President Biya's resolve to diversify political, economic and cultural ties. Turkey was accorded the status of observer member of the African Union in 2003 and since 2008, it is a non-regional member of the African Development Bank, ADB. (Martin Nkemngu, 2020: 3-15)

Trade exchange between Turkey and African attained 13 billion U.S. dollars in 2007. According to Turkish sources, the exchange will reach 30 billion US dollars in 2010. Cameroon appears set to pursue its intensification of cooperation ties with emerging industrialized countries like China, India, Iran, Turkey and Brazil.

Strengthening Cooperation Ties between Cameroon and Turkey with Turkish new ambassador to Cameroon

A new Turkish Ambassador, Ayse Saraç, was appointed to Cameroon in 2019, to replace the outgoing Turkish ambassador Husnus Murat Ulku. According to Eulalia Amabo's report, Ambassador Ayse Saraç is expected to inject a special impetus' to the cooperation between Cameroon and Turkey. President Paul Biya during a Unity Palace audience on Monday, July 15, 2019 received the letters of credence of ambassador Saraç in her capacity as the new Turkish Ambassador to Cameroon.

During her Sojourn as head of Turkey's diplomatic Mission to Cameroon, she would add another touch to deepen the continuously growing bilateral relations. The veritable impetus to the relations was given by the two Heads of state during their exchange visits. President Abdullah Gül of Turkey paid a two day official visit to Cameroon in March 2010 and President Paul Biya of Cameroon responded in an official visit to Turkey from March 25-28, 2013. According to Emmanuel Kendemeh of Cameroon Tribune, the two official visits of the two head of states went a long way in strengthening their cooperation and diplomatic ties.

In addition to strengthening those cooperation ties, Minister Adoum Gargoum and Ambassador Ayse Saraç of Turkey in an audience at the Ministry of External Relations talked on improving cooperation between both countries. Ties was on March 12, 2020 during which both personalities discussed deepening bilateral relations between both countries.

According to Eulalia Amabo of Cameroon Tribune who covered that story, she pointed out that Ambassador Ayse Saraç discussed elaborately with the Minister in areas of cooperation between Cameroon and Turkey with the possibility of enhancing them further. Cameroon and Turkey according to the ambassador are strategic partners and they have good bilateral cooperation in multi-dimensional domains such as business, technology, culture as well as at the international level. They also discussed elaborately on how to strengthen these cooperation ties further. One of those areas where the Turkish government strengthened diplomatic ties with the Cameroon government is in the Airline sector. Turkish Airline usually transport Cameroonians from Cameroon and back, successfully with almost no major problem. The Turkish people also recruit Cameroons to work for them. Moreover, the Turkish business men who are resident in Cameroon pay taxes to Cameroonian authorities that help the government to its administration.

During the last audience at the ministry of external relations on January 28, 2020, she discussed with the minister on the up-coming Turkey-Africa summit, the Turkish diplomat expressed satisfaction on the organization of the Major National Dialogue. She equally stated her countries readiness to support peace building in Cameroon. (Eulalia Amabo, 2020: 3-15)

Table 3: Turkish Ambassador Accredited to Cameroon from 2013

Names of Ambassador	Years of services or mission
Omer Faruk Dogan	2013
Husnu Murat Ulku	2018
Ayse Saraç	2019
Volcan Iskeci	2021

Source: Author's Compilation

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Relations between Cameroon and Turkey are positive with both Presidents having carried out official visits to each other's nation. Due to these friendly relations between both countries, several cooperation agreements have been arrived at in areas like, health, education, security and infrastructure; with the Turk Eximbank having financed 75% of the construction of the Japoma 50,000 capacity stadium in Douala, Littoral Region. (Eulalia Amabo, 2020: 3-15)

The Turkish NGO called AKAMAS usually help the vulnerable, marginalize or poor people in Cameroon. They also came to the aid of the Muslim community in Cameroon during Major Muslim Feasts such as, the Feast of The Ramadam and Feast of the Sacrifice. Food items such as bags of rice, cooking oil, sugar and cattle are offered the Muslim Community to slaughter and share among themselves. AKAMAS also made available financial aid for the construction of Muslim religious sites. Aids are also given to internally displaced person in Cameroon.

Formal relations between Turkey and Cameroon

In years past, the idea of trade with the African countries was impossible in Turkish society but today a number of Turkish businessmen invest in Cameroon with good economic earnings for Turkey and indeed Cameroon. According to the Republic of Turkey's Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA) (2017), Turkey-Cameroon relations date back to the emergence of Cameroon as an independent nation in 1960. Some years after Cameroon's independence, Turkey opened an Embassy in Yaounde, capital of Cameroon. Towards the end of the 1980s and early 1990s with the law on freedom of Association in Cameroon, commercial contacts between private business firms in Turkey and Cameroon were established. Turkey- Cameroon relations are part of a broader "Opening up to Africa" plan by the Turkish government in early 1998 as a move towards globalisation (Akinsaya, 2010: pp. 2-70). Turkish foreign policy for opening up to African countries, Cameroon in particular may, however, be viable if her policy would be beneficial for Turkish and Cameroon citizens. Therefore, on a general note, Turkey- Cameroon relations and state interests are both economic, social and political since in the present setting of international affairs the economic interest of a country cannot be pursued in isolation from its social and political interest or vice versa. As such, economic, social and political interests are complementary to one another. Similarly, the economic influence of a country in another country impinges on its political and social influence therein (Genc and Tekin, 2016).

Over the years, Turkey and Cameroon have maintained good political relations. Both Turkey and Cameroon are considered to have the political will to further improve bilateral relations in strategic fields. The reason is because both countries are members of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC). Cameroon and Turkey maintain close cooperation in international organizations (Murinson, 2006). Commercial and economic relations between the two countries have also been improving rapidly. The bilateral trade volume has increased more than threefold since 2015. Cameroon is one of the largest trade partner of Turkey in Sub-Saharan Africa as of 2017. There are many Turkish business men and companies, operating mainly in the construction, manufacturing, food, textiles and energy sectors (Akinsaya, 2010: pp. 2-70).

Furthermore, there have been high level state visits between both countries that have helped strengthen the relations between both nations. As a result of high-level mutual visits such as on the occasion of the visit of the President of Turkey, H.E. Mr. Abdullah Gül to Yaounde, Cameroon. From late 2000, new cooperation opportunities have been grasped in every field and the legal basis for bilateral relations between the two countries has been largely completed with the signing of agreements in political, military, economic, commercial, cultural and educational fields (Akinsaya, 2010: pp. 2-70).

Additionally, the Turkey- Cameroon relations have also witnessed movement of people between both countries parallel with developments in, trade, and there has been a consistent rise in arrivals of Cameroonian nationals to Turkey since 2000. The difference between arrivals and departures also reveals that as a trend, more Cameroonians are coming, and more Cameroonians are staying in Turkey. Departures of Cameroonians from Turkey have remained very high just like their arrivals since 2010 suggesting that at least some of those arriving from Cameroon are staying to do business, gain an education, or apply for asylum even with high visa fees. The numbers, however, are likely to be low due to the macro-institutional framework and meso-level constraints.

Success and failure of foreign policy

The Turkish foreign policy has been keenly followed by a large number of people over the years. Academics have tried to coin the changes and conceptualization that has brought about the new front of Turkish Foreign Policy (Kanat, 2014). In Cameroon, the Turkish policy has not had a difficult time to penetrate the market and especially, the military industry. The continued relations between Turkey and Cameroon suggest firstly, a mutually beneficial relationship that underscores a foreign policy success. The various bilateral relations both countries have had point to policy-making process, decision and political successes have been recorded. Further, the expansion of trade between both nations also indicates that the outcome of economic parleys by both nations have continued to meet the expected outcomes.

In addition, the relations between both nations have also recorded success in the war against terrorism. Since the inception of Boko Haram insurgency, Cameroon has made Turkey a strategic partner in the fight against Boko Haram. The strategic anti-terrorism partnership has brought Turkey closer to Cameroon. This is considered to be one of various factors that have determined the current state of the Turkey- Cameroon relations. Turkey has also penetrated the market and service economy over the years.

Projections into the Future

Against this background, what can we ascertain for the future of the Turkish- Cameroon relation. Answers to this question will be articulated below. These answers will be based on an analysis of observations and factual information rather than speculating on scenarios. The aim of this study is not to be exhaustive, but thought provoking. Similarities between Turkey and Cameroon

Any similarities between these countries would form a common ground that would no doubt help facilitate the advancement of bilateral relations. Luckily enough, one can see similarities between Turkey and Cameroon. Naturally, it goes without saying that the levels and patterns of development of the two countries are far from each other. Present-day socio-cultural parameters in Turkey and Cameroon have similarities despite their different historical backgrounds. For example, issues such as gender and traffic problems occupy the daily agenda of social life of the Cameroonian people as well as of the Turkish people. In domestic politics, issues of human rights and democratization remain on the agendas of both countries, despite the huge difference of progress between the two countries in these fields (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2019: pp. 3-17).

In foreign policy, both countries stand as regional powers in their respective regions. Their presence and active contribution is a key factor in the preservation of stability and peace in their turbulent surroundings. Likewise, their stability is vital for the stability of their regions. Inevitably, due to their position as regional powers, they also face similar foreign policy tactics and pressures in the international arena. Naturally, these similarities pave the way for a common understanding and sharing of experience between the two countries (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2019: pp. 3-17).

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General features of Cameroon beside these similarities, it is also important to ascertain the general features of Cameroon for, without elaborating on them it would be difficult to form a sound strategy for the advancement of bilateral relations. These characteristics can be listed roughly as follows:

From a socio-cultural perspective, the colonial background is important. Hence, nationalism and national pride is strong, especially among the social and political elites. Equal treatment and partnership are of prime importance rather than aid program, which remind Cameroonians of the old times when they lived at the mercy of their 'masters'. In political life, one witnesses the dominance of the state strata ruled by the executive over all facets of the society. This leads to the non-existence of an effective civil society (Eulalia Amabo, 2020: pp. 3-17).

The economic consequence of this structure is a state-controlled economy. Due to the lack of an efficient system of revenue collection and distribution, there is an insufficient infrastructure, a high level of unemployment and low personal incomes that result in a very low standard of living despite huge oil reserves. Cameroon is a petroleum producing country. The government relies to a great extent on crude oil export revenue. Therefore, the gradual decrease and volatility of oil prices on world markets has impaired the welfare of the country. (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2019: pp. 3-17).

There is a problem of instability. This risk is part of life where the functioning of the state is dependent on a country's leadership rather than on an impersonalized system of governance. The risk of instability is of prime importance particularly at present as Cameroon approaches the end of a seven year mandate by President Paul Biya. Yet, at the present time, uncertainty about the near future, which is supposed to witness historic changes, prevails. (Martin Nkemngu, 2010: pp. 2-17).

Generally speaking, in inter-state relations, state interests are divided into economic and political. However, in the present setting of international affairs, it is understood that the economic interests of a country cannot be pursued in isolation from its political interests or vice versa. In the era of globalization, economic and political interests have become heavily intertwined and complementary to one another. Economic power effects political power. Similarly, the economic influence of a country in another country duly impinges on its political influence therein. This is particularly valid in African countries as they attach the utmost importance and priority to their economic development as a means of disentangling themselves from long persisting patterns of poverty (Akinsaya A., 2010: pp. 1-19). What matters is to find the right combination to channel economic power in the service of political interests.

The establishment of a Turkish-Cameroon chamber of commerce will be of great importance because it can bring together the right buyers and suppliers to optimize trade. This body will provide a formidable and credible forum for trade promotion and it will help alleviate the problem of fraud, which remains a serious obstacle to the realization of the real potential for bilateral trade. In fact, such a body is in the pipeline in Cameroon. Once it comes into existence, the second stage should be relate this body to its counterparts in Turkey (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2019: pp. 3-17).

Having said that, one should also mention the difficulties in further increasing Turkish exports. The present Turkish export items are mainly directed to the well-off sections of Cameroon society and these constitute only ten percent of the Cameroon populace. Another obstacle is the cost of transport because of the distance between the two countries. A way to surmount these two obstacles could be to establish firms in Cameroon through either joint ventures or direct investment.

In this regard, setting up small and medium-sized enterprises aimed at serving the basic needs of the lower and middle classes would be beneficial. Manufacturing electrical appliances and household items in addition to automobile spare parts seems to be promising and reliable areas of investment. (Akinsaya A., 2010: pp. 1-19). Establishing such firms in Cameroon would reduce the cost of transport and of labour, thus increasing the competitiveness of these products. The low cost of these products would facilitate trading with neighbouring African countries. An agreement on the avoidance of double taxation would be instrumental in promoting such investments given the fact that an agreement on the mutual protection and promotion of capital investments has already been signed and its adoption is pending (Eulalia Amabo, 2020: pp. 3-17).

Beside trade between the private sectors, one should also explore the possibility of inter-state trade. In this regard, the exchange of Cameroon crude oil for Turkish goods and services should be assessed. In such an exchange, the Turkish side could contribute to the improvement of Cameroon public services by providing, for instance, public transport vehicles, health equipment for hospitals, educational materials for schools and even military equipment, once civilian rule is restored. Another promising area is the construction sector. The whole country, particularly, the political capital Yaounde, requires numerous construction projects. Some Turkish firms have already bid for various projects. The public sector is in need of infrastructure and dwellings. Everything lies in the hands of the state and its officials. Therefore, special strategies for securing state patronage are to be deliberated that must be well known by the private sector (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2019: pp. 3-17).

Similarly, given the magnitude of the need, there is an increased demand for cement. In this respect, exporting cement or establishing cement factories should also be explored. There is no doubt that the penetration into the economic life of Cameroon would also increase the economic influence of Turkey and thus, its political importance and relevance in the eyes of the Cameroonian leadership. In the organizations of which both countries are members, Turkey could more easily secure the support of Cameroon because of Turkey's increased political relevance. Likewise, Cameroon's positive interventions would facilitate the voicing Turkey's views and securing Turkish interests in international fora of which Turkey is not a member but Cameroon is, such as the group of the non-aligned countries. Naturally, any inter-state relation can be advanced if it is mutually beneficial. Therefore, when attempting to analyze the possible benefits for Turkey, one should also ask what Cameroon could gain from opening its economy to Turkey. This is extremely important because to enter the Cameroonian economy requires the consent of the Cameroonian leadership and state. Therefore, appropriate incentives should be provided to the Cameroonian side. (Eulalia Amabo, 2020: pp. 3-17). In this regard the following can be evaluated:

In the economic field, special funds for construction projects and Eximbank credits could be provided. Turkish experience in the implementation of free market economic policies would be very useful for the restructuring of the Cameroonian economy. This experience could be made available through technical visits and contacts between public and private sector representatives of both countries. The Protocol of the Joint Economic Commission provides a proper channel that can be further explored (Emmanuel Kendemeh, 2019: pp. 3-17).

In the socio-cultural field, the number and coverage of scholarships for Cameroonians could be increased. Enabling more Cameroonian students to study in Turkey; would help build the image of Turkey in the minds of the Cameroonian people. It would also in the long-term increase the number of influential friends of Turkey in Cameroon because those students would eventually join the upper levels of Cameroonian society (Eulalia Amabo, 2020: pp. 3-17).

Diplomatic Relations Between Cameroon and Turkey: A Beneficial Cooperation that has Come to Stay

In the field of politics, showing understanding for the existing problems in Cameroonian domestic politics, such as difficulties in improving her human rights record and democratization, would be conducive. In addition to such understanding, offering the experience of Turkey on these problems would be helpful to the leadership and society as a whole. On the other hand, Cameroon would appreciate the voicing of support in international arenas wherever appropriate. In this context, the establishment of the already agreed political consultation mechanism between the foreign ministries would be worth considering (Martin Nkemngu, 2010: pp. 2-17).

CONCLUSION

This article has reviewed the relations between Turkey and Cameroon along foreign policy lines. It was found that both nations have had smooth relations over the years culminating in foreign policy successes. Both nations have had informal and formal interrelations that have helped to bolster the objectives of the relations in the first instance. However, the article found out that the Turkey- Cameroon relations like most foreign policies have not been entirely devoid of policy failures. Therefore, Turkey-Cameroon relations as with any other country are based primarily on mutual benefits to both actors. However, it is recommended that foreign policies are insulated from political vendetta and clamp down actions by participating governments in order to avoid total breakdown of bilateral relations. It is also recommended that Turkish ventures in Cameroon participate more in corporate responsibility projects. As such, both countries should open up to each other, strengthened their diplomatic relations, improved on their economic cooperation and work in synergy, peace and harmony, for the development and success of both nations.

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